

FLUTTER-FREE DESIGN OF AERODERIVATIVE GAS TURBINE NOZZLES WITH SIMPLIFIED AERO-MECHANICAL MODELS

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ABSTRACT

This work presents a simplified procedure to design a flutter free airfoil geometry for aeroderivative gas turbine stator blade rows. The common workflow for a fully 3D flutter numerical assessment with an uncoupled method firstly involves a FE modal analysis to obtain the airfoil mode shapes which will be used for unsteady aeroelastic computations with moving airfoil.

Nozzle geometries are usually very complex: airfoils in a packet configuration and different mechanical features needed to attach the packet itself to the turbine casing make the structural meshing a non-trivial task.

The aim of this paper is to demonstrate how, in the early aero-mechanical design phases simplified models including only the airfoil geometry and the endwalls chunks can be efficiently used to design flutter-free components.

First of all, detailed comparisons between modal results from full and simplified mechanical models have been performed. Then, flutter computations have been carried out using modal results both from the full mechanical model (the sector or packet model) and two different simplified models (single airfoil models).

Finally, flutter results in terms of logarithmic decrement curves will be presented, showing the capability of this approach to guarantee flutter free geometries even from the early design stages. This aspect is essential to avoid blade-row redesign due to flutter issues which may occur during the final design of the airfoil.

NOMENCLATURE

dL_δ	Local work on a blade grid cell
\mathcal{L}	Aerodynamic work
\vec{c}	Blade surface velocity
\vec{n}	Blade surface normal
dS	Surface of CFD grid cell
n_d	Nodal diameter
N_P	Number of packet
E	Blade average kinetic energy
S	Blade surface
T	Vibration period

Greek:

δ	Logarithmic decrement
ρ_δ	Energetic damping surface density
ξ	Energetic damping ratio

Acronyms:

1F	1 st Flexural modeshape
1T	1 st Torsional modeshape
A/F	Airfoil
BC's	Boundary Conditions
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DOF	Degree Of Freedom
F/M	Full sector model
FEM	Finite Element Model
FPT	Free Power Turbine
IBPA	Inter Blade Phase Angle
IPPA	Inter Packet Phase Angle
LPT	Low Pressure Turbine
LRN	Low Reynolds Number
URANS	Unsteady Reynolds Average Navier-Stokes

INTRODUCTION

Flutter-free airfoil design is a challenging task especially when highly loaded and slender blades are conceived. To achieve this objective it is important to start assessing flutter stability in the early design phases to avoid expensive redesign of the final geometry when, taking into account only aerodynamic requirements, a suitable flutter stability flutter is not reached.

Nowadays numerical methods for flutter evaluation are mature and validated, yet they are still expensive from a computational point of view. For this reason, simplified models for both modal and CFD unsteady flutter analyses are appealing in order to include flutter assessment in the early phases of the design process.

Numerical structural analyses to obtain the modal characteristics of turbine blade-rows with or without cyclic symmetry conditions are based on well-established techniques. On the other hand, numerical methods to compute the unsteady response of a vibrating cascade (responsible for the flutter occurrence) can make use of different methodologies, (e.g. linear, time-linearized, harmonic balance or non-linear methods). The first aeroelastic numerical methods, developed at the beginning of the 1970s, were based on linear approaches where all the equations are linearized [1, 2]. Since the 1990s, time-linearized methods have been developed: according to these approaches, the flow is decomposed into a non-linear steady flow plus a small-perturbation harmonic unsteady flow [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. In recent years thanks to the growth in computer technology, non-linear methods have become a viable alternative and several non-linear (uncoupled and coupled with structural solver) approaches have been implemented [9, 10, 11, 5, 12, 13, 14]. Although computationally expensive, these methods are able to include non-linear effects into aeroelastic analysis. All these methods are well known in the literature and some comparisons among them have been already carried out by several authors [15, 16].

In this paper, simplified models to verify flutter-free design of gas turbine nozzles are presented and applied to a stage of a modern M&I engine Free Power Turbine. These approaches allow the reduction of computational requirements for both modal and flutter analyses in order to shorten the aeroelastic analyses, making them compatible with the early design phase timing of a turbine nozzle design loop. Usually these components are mounted in packets and an accurate aeromechanical characterization would require a modal analysis of the entire sector and also the unsteady flutter computation of a wide tangential multi-block domain. The simplified methods presented herein suggest the analysis of a single airfoil model in a typical tuned configuration without taking into account the packet assembly, or equivalently the analysis of the most active airfoil within the packet with a “single blade” approach usually employed for individually mounted blades. The results from simplified models are compared with the full sector analyses and these comparisons confirm the applicability of these simplified methods to assess the flutter behavior of nozzle segments with a significant saving of computational requirements.

1 Numerical Method for Flutter Assessments

The uncoupled flutter method used herein is based on the URANS Traf code. The CFD solver is able to solve pressure response due to the airfoil vibrations in single or cluster mode environment for tuned and mistuned rows [14, 17] thus implementing an uncoupled non-linear flutter prediction methodology.

The code [18, 19] solves the system of governing equations by using a dual-time stepping technique with an explicit stage Runge-Kutta integration algorithm on a cell-centered finite volume discretization of the flow domain. The unsteady Navier-Stokes equations are integrated with three point backward difference formula in time within a domain where the airfoil move according to the frequencies and mode shapes derived from modal analysis.

Time-sinusoidal blade vibrations of the aerodynamic surfaces are assigned to the aeroelastic calculation as input data, and the whole computational mesh is perturbed at each time step to follow the blade vibrations.

Traveling wave deformations are represented on a periodic sector with phase lagged conditions applied on periodicity surfaces [20]. Their implementation makes use of Fourier transforms to assign quantities on periodicity boundaries with appropriate time shifts to reproduce the analyzed Inter Blade Phase Angle or IBPA. This approach allows a limitations of the memory storage requirements.

For a row with N_p packets composed by N_b airfoils and for a given nodal diameter n_d , the IPPA can be defined as:

$$IPPA = \frac{2\pi}{N_p} n_d \quad \text{with } n_d \in \mathbb{Z} : -\frac{N_p}{2} < n_d \leq \frac{N_p}{2} \quad (1)$$

In case of $N_b = 1$, the equation leads to the classical IBPA definition. As already stated, the steady flow solution is used as flow initialization of the unsteady analysis with moving packet and each possible travelling wave deformation is computed until the solution reaches periodicity over the vibration period. Finally the aerodynamic work as defined in eq. 2, is used to assess row stability by integrating unsteady pressure on the airfoil surface over blade vibration period [21].

$$\mathcal{L} = \int_t^{t+T} \int_S (-p) \vec{n} \cdot \vec{c} dS dt \quad (2)$$

Once \mathcal{L} is computed, the energetic damping parameter ξ can be calculated to establish if the energy flow goes from the airfoil to the fluid (i.e. damping behavior, $\mathcal{L} < 0$) or vice versa. Dividing the aerodynamic work by the blade average kinetic energy, ξ is obtained, but for a better usage in dynamic analysis it may be useful to refer it as the logarithmic decrement δ .

$$\delta = 2\pi\xi = -2\pi \frac{\mathcal{L}}{8\pi E} \quad (3)$$

Due to δ is a global parameter which identify the damping behaviour of the airfoil only, to have additional information about the airfoil regions where the main work exchange occurs a density of energetic damping can be defined as follow.

$$\rho_{\xi} = \frac{-dL_{\delta}}{8\pi E \frac{dS}{S}} \quad (4)$$

This parameter can be plotted over the airfoil mode shape, highlighting the zones which mostly affects the global aerodynamic damping. In case of sector computation the critical damping ratio is referred to the whole packet: the aerodynamic work is computed over all the airfoils composing the packet, and also the mean kinetic energy is related to each sector mode.

2 Stage Layout and Mean Aerodynamic

Figure 1: Vane discretization with H-type grid

The stage under investigation has been already designed to meet required targets of aerodynamic performances by using CFD multistage computations and single row 3D steady analysis of this nozzle confirms the goodness of the aerodynamic design. Single stage steady solution was computed with structured H-type grid of about 1M cells (see Fig. 1), with $k - \omega$ turbulence model in a Wilcox's LRN formulation and will be used as flow initialization for the further unsteady analyses. Spanwise distributions at Full Speed, Full Load (FSFL) condition are extracted from multistage simulations (see table 1) and imposed for both steady and unsteady runs.

3 Modal Analysis

Modal analysis is aimed at determining natural frequencies and mode shapes of an elastic body in free vibration.

	inlet	outlet
α [deg]	-14.5	65.8
T [K]	1008.3	962.8
P_0 [bar]	4.1	4.0
Mach	0.25	0.59
<i>pressure ratio</i>	1:0.82	
Zweifel number	0.942	

Table 1: Average quantities from the multistage computations

Modal results represent the basic input for aeroelastic computations to confirm flutter free design of the turbine components. The modal analysis is performed with Ansys APDL and model setup guidelines for accurate modal computational of modes will be discussed in the following sections. This analysis is carried out following BHGE best practice criteria, and for this reason, most of the information cannot be provided in this paper to protect company's intellectual property. Classical uncoupled flutter analysis is based on single airfoil mode in a tuned configuration and this means the modal analyses are limited to one-pitch sector. When the airfoils are mounted in a packet, a larger solid domain must be simulated requiring an higher computational effort usually not suitable in preliminary design phases. In this context, it becomes necessary to define simplified models to speed up the analysis keeping an acceptable level of accuracy. At the early stages of a design process when the nozzle CAD model is still not fully available and/or officially released, it is recommended carry out single airfoil (A/F) modal analysis both to save time and provide a first feedback to address design changes. This approach has two major advantages. First, the A/F definition is available early at the design cycle. Second, it provides significant time saving for iterations between aerodynamic definition and aero-mechanical design. The mesh generation for a full sector model is demanding in time and human resource due to the complexity of its geometry, and so not fully automatically generated. A viable strategy is to perform a preliminary modal analysis including one airfoil geometry only and neglecting the platforms.

In the following paragraphs, the simplified model will be described and flutter results compared with the ones from full sector model which will be firstly presented to give an idea on the actual stage geometry.

3.1 Full Sector Model

A complete full sector FE model (F/M) including a casing portion is considered for the analysis. The constraints are applied to accurately reflect the mounting conditions of an actual nozzle in the engine. The nozzle exhibits a circumferential periodicity and to reproduce that cyclic sym-

metry constraints can be imposed to the upper and lower periodic bounds on the outer casing and inner seal/interlocking (Fig. 2b). To reproduce the connections between nozzle and casing interface, a contact region is defined, while axial constraints are applied at the interlocking region on the lower platform (Fig. 2a).

Figure 2: FEM setup for modal analysis

The nozzle modal shapes identified through this full sector modal analysis can be classified in two fundamental families: System and Airfoil Modes. The system modes which are usually assessed, are the first axial, bending and torsional modes, named 1A/SYS, 1F/SYS and 1T/SYS respectively. Regarding the airfoil family, first and second bending modes (1F and 2F), first and second torsional modes (1T and 2T) and first 2-stripe mode (1-2S) are considered. 1F airfoil mode is characterized by blade moving in tangential directions and platforms remain fixed, while 1T airfoil mode shows airfoils twisting around their longitudinal axis and platforms remain stable. For each mode at its proper frequency, a different airfoil within the sector shows the highest activity and so the highest displacements. As the sector includes multiple airfoils, several 1F and 1T natural frequencies can be computed.

In other words, 1F and 1T modes occur in arrays of a few adjacent modes falling into two narrow frequency bands.

System and airfoil mode frequencies are used to create a classical Campbell diagram, a graphical method tool useful to compare the frequencies of natural vibrations to frequencies of excitation forces and identify potential resonances. Operating and Idle speed ranges are considered for the mentioned assessment. The excitation and natural frequencies are plotted vs FPT rotational speed. Potential resonances are shown by the crossings between excitation and natural frequencies.

The design approach is to avoid crossings between excitation and component natural frequencies at operating and idle speeds.

3.2 Single Blade Model

In general, a single A/F analysis is carried out following the same procedure and guidelines as for the full sector model, nevertheless some basic differences must be properly highlighted. The major difference is how the model is constrained. In this kind of simplified model, the airfoil displacements are constraint at the top and bottom surfaces (Fig.3)

Figure 3: Simplified model for modal analysis

The boundary conditions (BCs) on mesh node degrees of freedom (DOFs) are chosen according to the best practices developed through various numerical runs and related data match with test results. The mentioned BCs are depending on airfoil and packet features like fillets and types of interlocking design. In Fig. 5a, Fig. 5b for 1F mode and in Fig. 6a, Fig. 6b for 1T modes it can be seen how the different methods of A/F constraints are affecting the resulting modal shape.

Moreover, the single A/F analysis is performed on a 'hot' geometry (activating the thermal expansion condition) while full sector analysis is carried out on a 'cold' geometry (temperature accounts only for Young's Modulus change). This can be a potential source of differences between the two analysis methods, not properly quantified in this paper.

3.3 Modal Results Comparison

The main objective of a complete flutter assessment is to predict potential instabilities involving all modes. Due to its simplified nature, the single A/F analysis cannot predict low frequency system modes (as only a single airfoil is included). Anyway, the most dangerous modes which can

Figure 4: Full sector modal analysis: most active airfoils

trigger flutter instability are the lowest airfoil modes (1F and 1T) and so, a single airfoil model can result useful for fast and reliable 3D flutter assessments since the conceptual and preliminary design phases. In fact, 1F and 1T frequency and shape are strictly dependent on A/F geometry and are only weakly influenced by the A/F boundary conditions. As a matter of fact, for the airfoil modes of interest, a good agreement between single A/F and full sector model analyses can be demonstrated as shown in Fig. 5 and Fig. 6. In the simplified modal setup several methods (A to F) for restraining a single A/F were compared to determine the optimum one yielding results closest to a full sector model analysis. For the 1F, the simplified model well represents the F/M mode shapes especially in the mid-span region where large displacements are found. In near endwall regions method F offered overall best fit. Method A gives good fit for higher order modes (2T/3T/1-2S) Methods A and D seem to be the best ones to match 1F frequencies and mode shapes, while methods A and E appear the best choices for 1T mode.

Figure 5: 1F mode shape comparison

Figure 6: 1T mode shape comparison

4 Flutter Result

In this section, flutter results in terms of logarithmic decrement, will be presented for the full sector and single A/F analyses and the results comparison will show the applicability of simplified models.

To make the all following aerodamping curves comparable, the modal displacements of the most active airfoil in the packet have been rescaled to take into account the modal mass of the different models which ensure a coherent kinetic energy (see Eq. 3) value to obtain the logarithmic decrement. Note that the aerodynamic damping computations assumes that the modal mass of the sector under investigation is normalized to unit.

4.1 Single Blade Analyses

To test the performance of simplified models for modal analysis, the relative logarithmic decrement curves will be compared to those derived from models with lower simplification levels. Running the full sector model, a modeshape for each airfoil can be obtained and looking at every one of

them, it is possible to see how even if the airfoils are geometrically identical, do not all vibrate with the same amplitude, and, in particular, one vibrates with greater amplitudes than the others as highlighted in Fig. 4. Assumed that the greatest energy exchange arises when major vibration occurs, the airfoil with the largest vibration amplitudes is compared with the simplified model. Since the simplified model is a single airfoil model, also the ones coming from the full blade analysis should be used in the same way. To put it simply, two single airfoil simulations are compared: the first vibrating with the mode shape extracted from the simplified model, the second vibrating as the airfoil with largest displacements coming from the full sector modal analysis.

4.1.1 1F Results

The stability assessment in terms of logarithmic decrement (red curve) for single A/F 1st bending mode shape is reported in Fig. 7. As can be seen all possible IBPAs have a positive aerodynamic damping confirming the overall flutter stability. Additionally, the comparison of the single airfoil analysis with the most active airfoil within the packet mode confirms the stability and curve shape, giving a first proof of the applicability of the simplified approach. Even if the single airfoil deformation does not exactly reproduce the actual vibration into the row composed by packets, yet it computes an approximated aerodynamic response of the most active airfoil which plays the main role in exchanging energy with flow during the packet travelling wave deformation.

Figure 7: **Single airfoil 1F modes logarithmic decrement**

To have a deeper insight on the results the surface distributions of energetic damping are reported in Fig. 8a and 8b; both analyses detect the major work exchanges in the mid-span region where the bending mode shapes under investigation show the largest displacements.

The logarithmic decrement curves in 7 are pretty close each other in magnitude; the exhibited gap is to ascribe both to a different response of the fluid during the vibration as

highlighted in 8a and 8b and to a slightly different mode shape.

Figure 8: **1F-damping surface density**

4.1.2 1T Results

In Fig. 9 flutter evaluations for single A/F 1st torsional mode shape is reported (orange curve).

All computed travelling waves exhibit a positive damping behaviour being the logarithmic decrement greater than zero for all IBPAs. Also for 1T, mode, the modal shape from the most active airfoil within the packet mode is in a well agreement with the simplified model, confirming the applicability of the simplified approach. The mode shape from the full packet modal analysis and the one from the simplified model fit well in shapes as highlighted in Fig. 6 and so the resulting curves of logarithmic decrement are even closer each other than those derived for 1F mode.

Looking to the energetic damping surface density in Fig. 10, negligible differences can be pointed out. The zones where the highest work exchange occurs, are similar between the single airfoil simplified method and the single airfoil model with the most active airfoil within the packet and they are consistent with the torsional mode shapes simulated.

4.2 Packet Analyses

To demonstrate the capability of simplified models to assess the flutter stability of stator vane packets, full packet aeroelastic analyses were also carried out. This approach requires the actual sector modes and tangential multi-block flutter computations: this means higher computational and time requirements for both modal and unsteady CFD analyses which are not guaranteed during the early design phases

Figure 9: **Single airfoil 1T modes logarithmic decrement**

Figure 10: **1T-damping surface density**

of turbine blade-rows. In this full approach, the row deformation is a superposition of packet travelling waves (IPPA, Inter Packet Phase Angle) and none of the vane deformation between adjacent airfoils reproduces the vane deformation of single airfoil simplified analyses. This is because in the single airfoil analyses the IBPA is imposed between all the adjacent identical airfoil (with same mode shape Fig. 11a), whereas in the packet analyses the IPPA is applied in one every four vanes (that is, between two 4-blade packets) where the two adjacent airfoil have different mode-shapes coming from the outer airfoils of the 4-blade sector mode (see Fig. 11b). Packet stability analysis can be presented by plotting the aerodynamic damping vs. the possible IPPAs (instead of the IBPAs) and as shown in Fig. 12, the two first packet modes (sector bending and torsion) are stable and the shapes of the aerodamping curves are quite similar to those derived with single airfoil simplified models.

The real values of damping are not shown in Fig. 12 as they are sensitive information, yet it is worth noting that the packet damping value are lower than the corresponding single airfoil ones.

In light of this, the full packet flutter results confirm the suitability of the single airfoil analysis coming from simplified approaches. Results from simplified models are thus enough to ensure flutter-free design for this type of rows saving computational requirements and, following this approach, fully 3D flutter analyses can be even included also during the early design phases of the blade-row.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This work has demonstrated the applicability of simplified models to assess flutter free design of a stage nozzle of gas turbine nozzle manufactured in a packet configuration.

In the first part of this paper, the main aerodynamic performances were presented in order to illustrate the row working conditions. Then, detailed results of the structural analysis carried out to compute component mode shapes were examined. Two different models are used: a detailed full model with the whole packet in cyclic symmetry conditions connected to the turbine casing, and a simplified one that simply include one single airfoil with different types of constraint on the airfoil root and tip, suitable to reproduce the actual airfoil modal behavior of the package.

After comparing the modal shapes obtained from the simplified model with the full one, the results are used to verify the row flutter stability with a non-linear uncoupled method.

Logarithmic decrement curves obtained from single airfoil models are compared with the corresponding travelling waves with airfoil mode shapes extracted from the most active airfoil within the F/M analyses. Both analyses do not detect flutter occurrence and confirm a flutter free design for the most prone modes to flutter instability, that are 1st bending and 1st torsion mode shapes. As expected, due to the similarity of mode shapes from single A/F and F/M analyses the curves of logarithmic decrement exhibit the same trend with also a good agreement in magnitude especially for the torsional vibration mode.

Finally, as confirmation of the results accuracy, full packet aeroelastic simulations were also carried out for bending and torsion F/M mode shapes. The logarithmic decrement curves coming from these accurate analysis are in good agreement with the ones obtained from single A/F analyses despite of a lower magnitude. These comparisons ensure the full applicability of the presented simplified models for flutter assessment in the early or intermediate phases of nozzle row design loop with a consistent reduction of computational efforts. In other words, the simplified approach can be completely embedded in the airfoil design process since its primordial phases ad allows the analyst performing quick and reliable fully 3D flutter stability checks.

Figure 11: Row deformation in A/F and F/M travelling wave

Figure 12: 1F, 1T packet modes logarithmic decrement

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